

Vision-guided symmetric dual arm picking of large objects with human-like robot motions

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Abstract—Dual-arm robot picking of large objects in industrial settings, which is often performed alongside human operators, requires not only precise control of multiple arms for stable grasping but also a safe and trustworthy human-robot interaction. A possible way to fulfill the latter requirement is the implementation of human-like movements, which enhances motion predictability by workers. In this paper, we propose a technical integration framework combining passivity-based adaptive force-impedance control for multi-arm manipulation, a vision-based system and a human-like Cartesian motion planning algorithm for dual arm picking of large objects. Our approach was tested in experiments with real robots handling large boxes.

Index Terms—Motion planning, Multi-arm manipulation, Integration platform

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotic manipulation with multiple arms is crucial for executing robot-assisted tasks, such as dual-arm picking and handling of large objects, either alongside or in coordination with human operators [1]. This challenge is complex, as it involves both (1) managing the coordination and interaction of multiple manipulators with their surroundings, and (2) ensuring that these interactions occur in unstructured environments in a manner that is safe and predictable for humans. Regarding point (1), which involves positioning the object as desired and maintaining a secure grip during movement, various solutions have been proposed in the literature, ranging from the development of low-level control laws to the design of high-level motion planning algorithms [2]. However, despite the strong theoretical contribution provided, these methods were usually deployed in controlled environments, where the model, position and orientation of the object are known in advance. With regard to point (2), ensuring safety is a critical factor in enabling the deployment of multi-arm manipulator systems alongside humans. One approach to achieve this is to make robot movements easily predictable for the human operator, which can be achieved by incorporating human-like characteristics in the produced motion [3].

In this work, we present a technical integration framework implemented in Robot Operating System (ROS) to perform dual arm picking of large objects. To develop it, we took advantage from our previous work on human-like motion generation [4], where we exploited a representation of the human hand motion based on functional Principal Component Analysis to design a motion planning algorithm in the Cartesian domain. For the control part, we leveraged the

Fig. 1. General scheme of the ROS framework. In orange the blocks represent the different ROS nodes implementing the different parts presented in our work while in blue the blocks represent the external hardware.

outcomes from [5], where the authors proposed a modular hybrid force/impedance control for multi-arm manipulation. The framework is complemented with a vision component, which exploits the data of an RGB-D camera to estimate the position and dimensions of the box to be manipulated and infer the possible contact point location to perform grasping. An overview of the proposed integration framework is presented in Fig. 1. The manuscript is structured as follows: first, we provide a brief description of the ROS technical integration framework. Afterwards, we describe the experimental setup we developed to test the framework, reporting and discussing the output of the experiments. Finally, we discuss the future steps to be addressed.

II. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

To build the whole framework, we exploited as base ROS Noetic, developing a set of ROS nodes which implement the different blocks and putting them in communication using ROS topics. In Fig. 1 a representation of the overall scheme is depicted. In our framework, 3 different types of nodes can be identified:

1) *Vision Node*: the task of this node is to process the point cloud recorded by the RGB-D camera and return the Oriented Bounding Box (OBB) representing the object and the desired contact point for each manipulator. The whole vision pipeline can be summarized in 4 parts: 1) the downsampling of the point cloud to reduce the computational load; 2) filtering to remove outliers; 3) the application of DBSCAN to isolate the cluster representing the object; and 4) the extraction of the OBB from the cluster and consequently the contact point for the arms.

2) *HL Motion Planner*: it implements the motion generation approach proposed in [4], which is based on functional Principal Component Analysis of the human hand motion to intrinsically guarantee the desired behaviour. It takes the information provided by the vision node and the state of the manipulators to generate the desired trajectory to be sent to the controllers as references.

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Fig. 2. Snapshot of a pick-up from random configuration task

3) *Hybrid Control*: this node implements two different parts functional for the implementation of the overall control: the modular force/impedance control law proposed in [5], and the momentum observer proposed in [6], which permits to estimate external wrench at the end-effector without the usage of a F/T sensor. It receives as input the desired pose and contact force from the planner and the actual state of the robot from the Franka Control Interface (FCI) and computes the desired torque command to follow both the pose and the force references.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The experimental validation consists of a set of pick-up actions of a large box (40.5x42x31cm, 0.780 Kg). The two main assumptions we made are: 1) the box has a homogenous density, which permits us to approximate the centroid found with the vision with the centre of mass of the object; and 2) we know in advance the force required to perform a non-prehensile picking, which depends on the friction between its surface and the end-effectors of the robots. The experimental setup includes two Franka manipulators positioned with a displacement of 1.3m along the local frames y -axis, while sharing the same local orientation. A soft-rubber hemispherical tip is mounted at the end-effector of both robots. The control parameters used for these tests are $k_{t,x}, k_{t,y}, k_{t,z} = 600N/m$, $k_{r,x}, k_{r,y}, k_{r,z} = 20N/rad$, $\delta_{imp} = 1cm$, $\delta_{frc} = 5cm$, $ee f_d = 10N$, $[k_p, k_i, k_d]^T = [1.5, 0.3, 0]^T$ and D_C is chosen to achieve critical damping behaviour. To implement the vision part of the pipeline we used an Intel[®] RealSense[™] Depth Camera D415 placed behind the two manipulators. We calibrated the relative pose between the camera and the robots through a custom procedure exploiting the AprilTag library.

A total of 18 pick-up tests were conducted with different initial conditions. Out of these, 17 experiments yielded successful outcomes, achieving the task of picking up the box without any issues related to contact loss. In the one remaining experiment, the result was unsuccessful during the reaching phase due to the joint limits of the manipulators. A set of snapshots depicting one of the tests performed can be found in Fig. 2. We computed the Root Mean Square Error for each trial to evaluate the trajectory tracking precision. The means and the standard deviations over all the tests performed for each arm are respectively $0.022 \pm 5.44 \cdot 10^{-04}m$ and $0.022 \pm 5.47 \cdot 10^{-04}m$.

To evaluate the Human-Likeness of the produced motion, several peculiar features were usually identified as metrics, such as arm postures, correlations between joints motion and kinematic temporal behaviour. However, most of them are mainly connected to an anthropomorphic kinematic structure. For this reason, we focus on evaluating the jerk of the motion produced by our framework leveraging the extensive literature

which supports this finding [7]. The averages of the median jerk at the Cartesian level obtained for each arm are respectively $(1.02 \pm 0.05) \cdot 10^{-05}m/s^3$ and $(1.19 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-05}m/s^3$ (for the planned trajectory is $(0.19 \pm 0.03) \cdot 10^{-05}m/s^3$). We can observe that, even in the presence of a hybrid control which manages the interaction between the two manipulators, we achieve a low level of jerk in the resultant motion of the two manipulators. Furthermore, even though the tasks involved are different, the jerk obtained is comparable with previous results on this topic [8].

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this work we propose a ROS framework that enables to integrate the human-like motion generation in [4], the modular hybrid force/impedance control in [5] and the data recorded by an RGB-D camera for the autonomous pick-up of large boxes. We tested this setup in a real scenario proving both the capability of performing the task under reasonable assumptions and maintaining the human-likeness of the motion.

We acknowledge that this is only the first step toward a completely autonomous dual-arm system able to operate in daily living environments alongside humans, and it should be developed and improved in several aspects such as proper estimation of inertial parameters of the object to regulate better the desired interaction force and the generalization to more complex tasks.

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